

IMPROVING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK SKILLS IN HIGHER EDUCATION ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation. This article emphasizes the importance of independent work in building the capacity of young people in higher education, the full achievement of the objectives of the lesson in the classroom, the interdependence and consistency of auditorium topics and topics of independent work, students read. The adequacy of the material base for the study and the need to ensure that the emerging cadres become more capable.

Key words: independent work, ability to work independently, tasks requiring independent work, analytical geometry, space plane and its properties.

Independent work is the acquisition of knowledge outside of school or university classes without the help of a teacher. At the same time, it is an integral part of the cognitive process. The higher education system plays a special role in creating the necessary conditions for students to improve their independent work skills and to work in accordance with the requirements of the time . [5]

Improving the quality of education also in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Ta'lim to'g'risida" ORQ-637, adopted by the Legislative Chamber on May 19, 2020 and approved by the Senate on September 23, 2020 , students' education in different forms (in-service education (full-time); in-service education (part-time, evening, distance); dual education; family education and independent work ; education and training of adults; inclusive education; external education; personnel training in the field of defense, security and law enforcement activities) are defined. [1]

Therefore, taking into account the above, improving the organization of independent work, strengthening the motivation for independent learning is an important task. In the process of higher education, it is possible to acquire any complex knowledge due to the effective use of thinking operations. Students become familiar with the functional and operational aspects of mathematical thinking (concept, judgment, conclusion), and also try to use all their intellectual reserves to use them independently. The conditions for independent education in mathematics are provided for all (individual, private, general, conflicting, hypothetical, negative) forms of judgment. They try to use inductive (direction of thoughts from specific to general) and deductive (direction of thoughts from general to specific cases) ways of drawing conclusions in a certain way in cognitive activities. Acquiring information by understanding the essence of concepts (single, specific, general, obvious, abstract, collective) ensures the stability of knowledge. All this is the basis for the development of mathematical thinking. During the lesson, the teacher explains the topic defined in the plan. This process is more of a teacher-centered process. A student's independent study of the subject outside of class will make the subject take a firm place in his understanding. Especially mathematics science from the student more _ independent by reading to learn Demand is a science that does . Lesson during mathematics from science teacher _ something one of the subject theoretical part and partially him in practice supporting shows . [2] Subject deep by learning get for student independent way more by reading to learn necessary _ To the topic circle more _ example and issues solve mathematics science deep of learning basis is considered Mathematics science of topics each in one being studied object about rules , theorems , definitions , properties and their except cases there is will be Because of this lesson process of the subject each one feature study _ for enough it won't be . That 's it cases independent work necessity is born _ Such of circumstances one how many below showing _ let's go :

We are 1st year mathematics study _ methodology in the direction " Analytical " geometry " science example as take we will show . Independent work about statement to do for we are optional way above telling one of the passed science topic choose we can

In space plain given , his different equations and properties

Auditorium lesson during of the plane Cartesian coordinates in the system given , his different equations and its normal vector about statement will be done . This is the lesson main part organize does _ Reinforcement for topic according to one how much example and issues taking off is displayed .

$Ax + By + Cz + D = 0$ (1)equation derivation is the main part of the lesson.(1) equation of the plane common in appearance is called the equation 1 of the plane coordinates in the system location shown ; 1- drawing

1- drawing

This is us with what we mean , in classes information not given the rest of the plane private cases and another properties about study _ of students to themselves link will be done . Below such of cases one how much stopping _ let 's go

Link 1

Above we $Ax + By + Cz + D = 0$ mentioned that the equation is the general equation of the plane. (this on the ground $A^2 + B^2 + C^2 \neq 0, \forall A, B, C \in R$) (1)in the equation A, B, C and D through the coefficients, we show about the location of the plane in the Cartesian coordinate system. (1)let the equation be an equation defining a plane in space . α

Case 1: If $Ax + By + Cz + D = 0$ in Eq $A = 0$ If the general equation of the plane is as follows : comes : $By + Cz + D = 0$. In that case our our plane α is parallel to $By + Cz + D = 0$ the coordinate axes . Ox condition for drawing 1.1 passed.

1.1- drawing

Case 2: If $Ax + By + Cz + D = 0$ in Eq $B = 0$., we have $Ax + Cz + D = 0$

In that case α the plane Oy is parallel to the axis. Figure 1.2 is cited below for this case.

1.2 - drawing

Case 3: If (1) in Eq $C = 0$ if , of the plane common in appearance equation the following appearance takes :

$$Ax + By + D = 0$$

From this our it turns out to be parallel to α the plane Oz axis. Figure 1.3 Oz shows a plane parallel to the axis.

1.3 - drawing

Case 4: If (1) in α the equation $D = 0$, our plane $(0,0,0)$ passes through the coordinate origin, that is, the point. Figure 1.4 shows the given situation.

1.4 - drawing

Case (1)5: If $A = 0, D = 0$ equation $By + Cz = 0$ to look will come and given plain Ox contains an arrow. The given situation is represented in diagram 1.5.

1.5 - drawing

Case (1)6: If $B = 0, D = 0$ equation $Ax + Cz = 0$ to look will come and given plain Oy contains an arrow. The given situation is represented in diagram 1.6.

1.6 - drawing

Case 7: If (1)in $\alpha Eq D = 0, C = 0$ our plane Oz contains an arrow. Figure 1.7 shows the given situation .

1.7- drawing

Case 8: If in (1)the equation $A = 0, C = 0,$ the equation of the plane $By + D = 0$ appears, that is, $y = \frac{-D}{B}$ it is equal to a constant number. From this, there will be a plane parallel to our given plane . xOz Figure 1.8 shows the given situation .

1.8- drawing

Case 9: If in (1) the equation $A = 0, B = 0,$ the equation of the plane $Cz + D = 0$ appears, that is, $z = \frac{-D}{C}$ it is equal to a constant number. From this, there will be a plane parallel to our given plane . xOy Figure 1.9 shows the given situation .

1.9 - drawing

Case 10: If in (1) the equation $C = 0, B = 0,$ the equation of the plane $Ax + D = 0$ appears, that is, $x = \frac{-D}{A}$ it is equal to a constant number. From this, there will be a plane parallel to our given plane . yOz Figure 1.10 shows the given situation.

1.10 - drawing

We are above α we mentioned about the location of the plane relative to the coordinate axes.

Link 2:

Okay to us Cartesian coordinates in the system ends M_1, M_2, M_3 at points has been triangle and $\alpha: Ax + By + Cz + D = 0$ plain given let it be We see

The issue that arises is Cartesian coordinates in the system triangle and of the plane mutually how cases location about Let us M_1, M_2, M_3 take the coordinates of the points as corresponding $(x_1, y_1, z_1), (x_2, y_2, z_2), (x_3, y_3, z_3)$ and they are through to the following have we will be

$$Ax_1 + By_1 + Cz_1 + D = m_1,$$

$$Ax_2 + By_2 + Cz_2 + D = m_2,$$

$$Ax_3 + By_3 + Cz_3 + D = m_3,$$

$$m_1, m_2, m_3 \in R$$

Above given m_1, m_2, m_3 depending on the values of the numbers α plane and $\Delta M_1M_2M_3$ coordinates in the system mutually location cases cause let 's go

Case 1: If m_1, m_2, m_3 the value of s $m_1 = m_2 = m_3 = 0$ takes the value at the same time, then M_1, M_2, M_3 the points α lie in the plane. From this $\Delta M_1M_2M_3 \in \alpha$ come comes out ie given triangle too α

Case 2: If m_1, m_2, m_3 the values of s satisfy the condition simultaneously $m_1 \neq m_2 \neq m_3$ and have the same signs, i.e., $m_1, m_2, m_3 > 0$ none $m_1, m_2, m_3 < 0$ of the points α belong M_1, M_2, M_3 to the plane and lie on the same side of it. This $\Delta M_1M_2M_3 \cap \alpha = \emptyset$ means that the plane and the triangle do not intersect.

Case 3: If m_1, m_2, m_3 the signs of are different, ie

$$1) m_1, m_2 > 0 \text{ va } m_3 < 0 \text{ (yoki } m_1, m_2 < 0 \text{ va } m_3 > 0),$$

$$2) m_2 m_3 > 0 \text{ va } m_1 < 0 \text{ (yoki } m_2 m_3 < 0 \text{ va } m_1 > 0),$$

3) $m_1 m_3 > 0 \text{ va } m_2 < 0$ (yoki $m_1 m_3 < 0 \text{ va } m_2 > 0$) if one of the conditions is true, then $\Delta M_1M_2M_3 \cap \alpha \neq \emptyset$ the sides of the triangle and α the plane have a common point. Instead of information again that's it to say should , if the triangle and plain for above given of conditions desired one appropriate if they are for common point two will be

Case 4: If m_1, m_2, m_3 any one of is equal to zero, then to that value suitable point to the plain belongs to will be Okay $m_1 = 0$ if we assume that $M_1(x_1, y_1, z_1)$ the

coordinates of the point $Ax + By + Cz + D = 0$ satisfy the equality, then M_1 the point α belongs to the plane.

Case 5: m_1, m_2, m_3 Any two of them are zero if α , then α lies in a plane $\Delta M_1 M_2 M_3$ with one side completely α . [4]

Here we are above analytical geometry from the course students independent to work which directs of subjects one is " In space plain given , his different equations and " properties " . one how many links through stopping we passed See _ as we are students independent work through the subject deep and sure learns _ Students independent performance for the first in line lesson during being taught to the object relatively interest wake up need _ From this except independent study _ for separated of subjects students to learn for convenience ie the audience lessons with duration one different to be of students independent work skills efficiency increases .

Independent performance of tasks related to improving the organization of independent work requires students to use mathematical thinking operations (analysis, synthesis, comparison, comparison, clarification, abstraction, grouping, categorization, generalization, systematization) and forms (concept, judgment, conclusion). [5]

Improving the organization of independent work in HEIs - introducing students to educational activities or educational methods is considered special in the development of mathematical thinking . In particular, teaching students how to look at mathematical concepts and mathematical situations from different points of view and how to transfer it to the situation (situation) gives high results. It should be emphasized that, as a rule, the transfer of mathematical methods is carried out "at once", gradually, "by breaking and fixing", revising, reorganizing the content, moving from visual material to mathematical (logical) material. There are views like

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